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RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Latchup screening with the dose-rate testing</i>
Project TA identifier	<i>TA10-354</i>
General application	<i>Test methods development</i>
Type of test	<i>SEE</i>
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Date(s) of the experiment	<i>19-21/11/2024</i>
Facility	<i>UCL</i>
Amount of access granted (unit of access: 1h)	<i>16</i>

Objectives of the experiments

In the project we aimed to collect high-quality data from both heavy-ion and prompt-dose tests to facilitate prediction of heavy-ion induced Single Event Latchups by means of prompt-dose testing. Irradiating multiple component types from a single family and manufacturer would help exclude manufacturing technology variations, refining the initial model linking latchup test results under heavy ions and prompt-dose.

This report concerns the heavy-ion test results.

Experiment test report

1. Introduction

We chose 4 ADC types from the Nisshinbo manufacturer to perform Single Event Latchup (SEL) characterization with heavy ions: NA2200BDAE2S, NA2202NBAE2S, NA2203NBAE2S and NA2204NBAE2S. These components were not tested with heavy ions yet, but we expected to observe SEL, as it is common in CMOS ADCs.

Due to problems with sample preparation, we managed to perform tests on only one component: NA2200BDAE2S. Chemical etching was too aggressive for pins of QFN packages, and the components in these packages were not possible to solder to the PCB board. See figures 1 and 2 below with example samples photos. In this case, the test objective was changed to characterize the available DUT NA2200BDAE2S in various bias conditions.

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Figure 1: NA2200BDAE2S sample with the package chemically etched.

Figure 2: NA2204NBAE2S sample with the package chemically etched and pins damaged.

2. Test setup and test conditions

The test setup consisted of the power supply unit, current monitoring and display of the return current with the oscilloscope, and current limiter. The delatching and SEL counting was performed manually. The device was not destroyed during the SEL with current limiting used. Test was performed in vacuum.

The power supply range of the NA2200BDAE2S is 2.7 to 5.5 V. The DUT was tested in the full supply range with heavy ions with LETs in range from 20.4 MeV.cm²/mg to 88.39 MeV.cm²/mg. The DUT was not performing any specific operations during the irradiations, but only powered up. The temperature of the DUT was not controlled during the irradiation.

3. Test results

Summary of the NA2200 heavy ions irradiations is given in a table below.

Run#	LET [MeV.cm ² /mg]	Supply voltage [V]	Flux [p/cm ² /s]	Fluence [p/cm ²]	Number of SELs observed	Comments
1.10	32.4	5.5	5E+3	1E+7	185	
1.11	32.4	2.7	5E+3	1E+7	0	No SEL, but the current draw was changing between 0.7/1.0/1.4/2.5 mA values randomly (both increasing and decreasing) during the irradiation.
1.12	32.4	4.1	5E+3	3E+6	0	Random changes of the current in range up to 11 mA, similarly to run 1.11.
1.13	32.4	4.1	1.5E+4	1E+7	12	No SEL was observed until the fluence of 4.5E+6, then the 100 mA micro-SEL was observed and soon a series of 12 SELs.
1.14	32.4	4.8	1.5E+4	1E+7	117	SELs observed rather in series.
1.15	32.4	4.8	5E+3	1E+7	61	Decreased flux with regards to the previous run resulted in decreased number of SELs observed.
1.18	20.4	5.5	1.6E+4	1E+7	0	Random changes of the current in range up to 17 mA, similarly to runs 1.11 and 1.12.
1.19	46.1	5.5	5E+3	2E+6	69	
1.20	46.1	5.5	1E+3	1E+6	32	
1.21	46.1	4.8	1.3E+3	1.5E+6	20	
2.2	46.1	4.1	5E+3	1E+7	6	Similarly to run 1.13, the 100 mA microSEL

						was observed at fluence level of 1E+6, then 6 SELs are observed until the fluence of 2E+6, and no more SELs are observed later until the final fluence of 1E+7 is reached.
2.4	62.5	5.5	1E+3	1.65E+6	50	
2.5	62.5	4.8	1E+3	2.48E+6	50	
2.6	62.5	4.1	5E+3	1E+7	1	
2.7	72.2	5.5	1E+3	1.05E+6	51	
2.8	72.2	4.8	1E+3	2.8E+6	51	
2.9	72.2	4.1	5E+3	4.2E+6	51	
2.10	88.4	4.1	5E+3	4.28E+6	51	
2.11	88.4	4.8	2E+3	9.1E+5	51	
2.12	88.4	4.8	1E+3	1.59E+6	51	The flux was reduced with regards to the previous run, and the resulting cross section is lower.
2.13	88.4	5.5	1E+3	8.6E+5	51	
2.14	32.4	5.5	5E+3	1E+7	58	Alternative test method used: the DUT was power cycled each time the microSEL (above 10 mA) or SEL are observed, but only SELs (direct surges to 150 mA) are counted.
2.15	32.4	4.8	5E+3	1E+7	8	Alternative test method (as described in run 2.14) used.

SELs were not observed for the LET = 20.4 MeV.cm²/mg when the device was supplied with 5.5 V and was not observed for the LET = 32.4 MeV.cm²/mg when the device was supplied with 2.7 V (it was the only test performed for the 2.7 V condition, in fact the LET threshold might be even higher). The SEL cross-section was measured and plotted for the LET values up to 88.4 MeV.cm²/mg, and for supply voltage levels: 4.8 V and 5.5 V. The device has shown dependence of the SEL sensitivity on the supply voltage. The DUT experienced more than a thousand SELs during the test campaign, and the electrical parameters suggest that the SELs did not destroy the DUT.

Two specific phenomena were observed in our tests: micro-SELs promoting SELs and SEL cross-sections varying with the flux. The phenomena are probably resulting from the test setup limitations (no thermal control, failure of the de-latching circuit).

4. Conclusions

The DUT has pretty strong dependence of the SEL cross section from the operating voltage. This feature might be used in future tests with other beam types to compare if the DUT response is changed under changed bias conditions.

No SEL observed at 2.7 V and with 32.4 MeV.cm²/mg.

However, the irradiations were not performed in the worst-case temperature conditions (the chip was not heated up).

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	
Data for Thesis	
Follow-up experiment at same facility	
Follow-up experiment at another facility	X
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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